

DETERMINATION OF SOLAR POSITION AND DAY LENGTH FOR PARTICULAR LOCATION

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ABSTRACT:

Utilization of solar energy using solar photovoltaic (PV) cell is a promising and growing field. Energy utilization is optimum when the sun is directly overhead and sunrays fall perpendicularly on a solar PV module. Hence, exact position of the sun in sky throughout a day is an important factor to know while designing and installing a solar panel. In this paper, an algorithm to determine altitude and azimuth angles that specifies the sun's position at Jabalpur (Madhya Pradesh, (23.1815°N, 79.9864°E)) precisely has been developed. It takes latitude, longitude, date and deference of local time from Greenwich Mean Time as input and logically calculates the angle. These results can be incorporated in design to orient a solar panel automatically without requiring any complicated tracking mechanism.

INTRODUCTION:

The sun is one of the fundamental energy sources in the universe. In the 21st century, ever increasing energy demand may be fulfilled with the help of solar energy that reaches the earth. Efficient and economic harnessing of clean solar power is very important for fulfillment of today's rapid growing energy need and also helps stop any types of environmental damage. Every day the sun radiates an enormous amount of energy in form of sun rays. It is the primary energy source for earth. The earth receives energy from the sun as electromagnetic radiation at extremely large rate i.e. 1.7×10^{17} watt. Daily the amount of energy that strikes each country is more than the energy which they need for power generation.

Photovoltaic cell is one of the supreme technologies available now to harness solar radiation and generate electricity. Amount of energy generated from a solar panel, consisting of large number of PV cells, depends on radiation quality and angle of incidence of sunrays. A solar module can generate maximum electricity when radiation falls vertically on solar panel. However, it is very difficult task to use solar energy because angle of incidence of sun rays are change continuously. So, the most challenging task is to tilt the solar panel at an angle to the horizontal surface throughout the day to fulfill the requirement of a 90

angle between the rays of the sun and surface of the solar module.

Parameters like latitude, longitude, season, dust, pollution and time of a day at a given location affect the position of the sun and amount of solar energy reaching there. Whether due south or due north depends on exact latitude of the location. So, depending on the above parameters there is a need to know the sun position in the sky with respect to a solar photovoltaic panel.

To position a panel directly towards the sun at all times, sometimes a solar tracking system is installed to determine the direction of incoming sunrays. But this is not only complicated but also costly. The most common approach though is to compromise and install the module at an optimum tilt angle so that surface of the module is perpendicular to the direction of radiation at solar noon on the equinox day, i.e. the panels tilts at an angle equal to the latitude of that location.

In this paper an attempt has been done to find out the sun position at Jabalpur i.e. at any time of a day by using standards formulae.

NOMENCLATURE:

δ → Sun declination angle
 ϕ → Latitude of location
 θ_z → Zenith angle
 α → Elevation angle of the Sun

THEORY:

The seasons occur because the Earth's axis of rotation is not perpendicular to its orbital plane (the "plane of the ecliptic") but currently makes an angle of about 23.44° (called the "obliquity of the ecliptic"), and because the axis keeps its orientation with respect to an inertial frame of reference. As a consequence, for half the year the Northern Hemisphere is inclined toward the Sun while for the other half year the Southern Hemisphere has this distinction. The two moments when the inclination of Earth's rotational axis has maximum effect are the solstices.

An equinox is an astronomical event in which the plane of Earth's equator passes through the center of the Sun which occurs twice each year, around 20 March and 23 September. On an equinox, day and night are of approximately equal duration all over the planet. They are not exactly equal, however, due to the angular size of

the sun and atmospheric refraction. To avoid this ambiguity, the word equinox is sometimes used to mean a day in which the durations of light and darkness are equal.

The equinoxes, along with solstices, are directly related to the seasons of the year. In the northern hemisphere, the vernal equinox (March) conventionally marks the beginning of spring in most cultures, while the autumnal equinox (September) marks the beginning of autumn. In the southern hemisphere, the vernal equinox occurs in September and the autumnal equinox in March.

A solstice is an astronomical event that occurs twice each year (in June and December) as the Sun reaches its highest or lowest excursion relative to the celestial equator on the celestial sphere.

For an observer on the North Pole, the sun reaches the highest position in the sky once a year in June. The day this occurs is called the June solstice day. Similarly, for an observer on the South Pole, the sun reaches the highest position on December solstice day.

Latitude(ϕ) :- The latitude of the place is the angle the radial line joining the place and the center of the earth forms with its projection on the equatorial plane can be said to be plane with latitude zero degree and it bisect the earth into two hemisphere.

Fig 1: Latitude of the location

Declination angle: - Declination angle is sun rays' angle of incidence on the earth on monthly and seasonal basis. In other words, it is the angle made by sun rays on the equatorial plane. The other name of declination angle is "the angle of deflection" and it is indicated with the symbol ' δ '.

$$\delta = 23.45 * \sin \left(\left(\frac{360}{365} \right) * (D - 81) \right) \quad \dots(1)$$

Here, D is Day

Fig 2: Elevation angle of the sun, zenith angle

Hour angle: It is an angle through which the moves across the sky its takes one hour for sun to cover 15° angular distance in sky.

$$H = 15 * (LST - 12) \quad \dots (2)$$

Here, LST is local solar time

Zenith angle (θ_z): It is the amount of angle between the sun's direction and the vertical axis. On horizontal plane, zenith angle is 90° between sunrise and sunset, and 0° at midday (12:00).

$$\cos \theta_z = \cos \delta \cdot \cos \phi \cdot \cos H + \sin \delta \cdot \sin \phi \quad \dots(3)$$

Solar elevation angle (As): The amount of angle created by the sun's direction and the horizontal axis. As it completes the zenith peak to 90° , solar elevation angle is:-

$$\alpha = 90^\circ - \theta_z \quad \dots (4)$$

Length of days: The length of the day, either: (a) the time between sunrise and sunset (i.e. the duration of daylight), especially as it varies at different times of the year or at different latitudes; or (b) the time from one sunrise to the next (on earth currently 24 hours).

$$\text{Day Length} = 2(\arccos(-\tan \phi * \tan \delta)) / 15 \quad \dots(5)$$

Following steps were taken to reach the conclusion:-

- 1) The value of the sun's declination by taking the different days of a year in account in equation 1
- 2) The value of the angle of elevation of the sun evaluated by using the equation 2, by substituting the value of the latitude of the location, hour angle and sun's declination.
- 3) To evaluate the sun's elevation at different local solar time hour angle is used calculated by equation 4.
- 4) To evaluate the length of the day throughout the year equation 5 is used with the variables as latitude of the location and sun's declination angle.

METHODOLOGY:

In order to achieve objective the whole methodological process is selected and developed very carefully.

After the initialization of the process and the steps are finalized, the sun declination angle, Hour angel, Zenith angle and elevation angle of the Sun is obtained. Calculation of sun declination angle equation [01] is done by taking days as a variable.

Calculation of hour angle is done [02] as per the local solar time of the particular location.

With the help of sun declination angle (δ) and hour angle (H), calculation of Zenith angle [3] is done.

Calculation of elevation angel [4] of sun is done by using Zenith angle.

RESULTS:

Results are obtained by the above mentioned methodology.

Day	Declination	9 O'clock	10 O'Clock	11 O'Clock	12 O'Clock	13 O'Clock	14 O'Clock	15 O'Clock	16 O'Clock	Day Length(hr)
1	-23.011445	26.37555	35.35876	41.54491	43.79121	41.54491	35.35876	26.37555	15.60738	10.60403796
15	-21.269127	27.5677	36.79198	43.19442	45.53353	43.19442	36.79198	27.5677	16.58312	10.72172988
30	-18.042372	29.73546	39.41089	46.23482	48.76028	46.23482	39.41089	29.73546	18.36086	10.93190196
45	-13.619401	32.6107	42.91275	50.36465	53.18325	50.36465	42.91275	32.6107	20.7276	11.20679935
60	-8.2934602	35.89795	46.96006	55.25884	58.50919	55.25884	46.96006	35.89795	23.45192	11.523468
75	-2.4176604	39.25445	51.14141	60.50878	64.38499	60.50878	51.14141	39.25445	26.26866	11.86230736
90	3.61843099	42.33984	55.01439	65.6339	70.42109	65.6339	55.01439	42.33984	28.91767	12.20712986
105	9.41461933	44.8816	58.18305	70.10432	76.21727	70.10432	58.18305	44.8816	31.18845	12.54291659
120	14.5866156	46.73737	60.40891	73.42058	81.38927	73.42058	60.40891	46.73737	32.95649	12.85292742
135	18.7915148	47.92013	61.70097	75.33068	85.59417	75.33068	61.70097	47.92013	34.19453	13.11678385
150	21.750531	48.56142	62.29173	76.07268	88.55319	76.07268	62.29173	48.56142	34.9502	13.31117591
165	23.2674804	48.82595	62.48547	76.22503	89.93517	76.22503	62.48547	48.82595	35.29883	13.41424433
180	23.2417889	48.82184	62.48282	76.2238	89.96087	76.2238	62.48282	48.82184	35.29315	13.41247747
195	21.6751598	48.54713	62.28014	76.06093	88.47781	76.06093	62.28014	48.54713	34.93219	13.30611915
210	18.6714611	47.89069	61.67124	75.28904	85.47412	75.28904	61.67124	47.89069	34.16181	13.10906393
225	14.4298389	46.6874	60.3512	73.33347	81.23249	73.33347	60.3512	46.6874	32.90677	12.8433233
240	9.23151406	44.8084	58.09294	69.97298	76.03417	69.97298	58.09294	44.8084	31.12121	12.53216002
255	3.42113706	42.24561	54.89609	65.47246	70.22379	65.47246	54.89609	42.24561	28.83544	12.19582531
270	-2.6160624	39.14638	51.00611	60.33493	64.18659	60.33493	51.00611	39.14638	26.17716	11.85096221
285	-8.4798161	35.78657	46.82213	55.08942	58.32284	55.08942	46.82213	35.78657	23.35917	11.51258129
300	-13.781355	32.50758	42.78656	50.21434	53.0213	50.21434	42.78656	32.50758	20.6425	11.19695497
315	-18.169187	29.65132	39.30891	46.11573	48.63347	46.11573	39.30891	29.65132	18.29176	10.92381247
330	-21.352396	27.51106	36.72377	43.11571	45.45026	43.11571	36.72377	27.51106	16.53673	10.71617747
345	-23.119934	26.30085	35.26911	41.44204	43.68272	41.44204	35.26911	26.30085	15.54628	10.59660029
360	-23.354614	26.13908	35.07503	41.21945	43.44804	41.21945	35.07503	26.13908	15.41398	10.5804655
365	-23.086532	26.32386	35.29672	41.47371	43.71612	41.47371	35.29672	26.32386	15.56509	10.59889164

The Above tabulated results which are generated by the above mentioned methodology shows the intensity of sun rays in the given time of frame for the selected region. As we see in the result the intensity of sun rays is found maximum at 12:00 PM.

Fig.3: Graph Showing Sun Declination Angles of considered location for 365 Days

It can be seen in Fig.3 that the correlation of the Sun Declination angle and days is Sinesodal in nature, which varies from -23.011(winter) to +23.24(summer), and the point of intesection with x axis shows the Equinox.

Fig.4: Graph Showing Sun's Elevation Angle of considered location for 365 Days

The Fig.4 shows the results of varition in intensity of Sun's rays through out the year. It can also be seen from the above graph that maximum intensity is obtained on 181th Day of the year.

Fig 5: Graph showing day lengths for considered location for 365 days

The Fig.5 shows the results of varition in length of days(in hours) through out the year at the location taken for study.It can also be seen from the above graph that maximum time when sun is visible is on 181th day of the year.

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